

Effect of School Environment on the Planning Skills of Learning Disabled Boys and Girls

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Abstract

This study attempts to examine the effect of different dimensions of school environment on the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls. The hypothesis of the study is that there is no significant examine the effect of different dimensions of school environment on the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls. The researcher has used descriptive survey method in this study. The investigator adopted random sampling technique to select 25 secondary schools of district Haridwar. The investigator identified the learning disabled students then selected sixteen learning disabled students from the identified learning disabled students from each school. In this way, the investigator selected the required four hundred learning disabled students randomly. Planning Skill is the dependent variable and school environment is the independent variable of the present study. Mean, S.D. and two-way analysis of variance have been used for the statistical analysis. Findings revealed that there was a significant difference in the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls. Learning disabled girls were found to have better planning skills as compared to learning disabled boys. A significant effect of creative stimulation, cognitive encouragement, acceptance, permissiveness, rejection and control has been found on the planning skills of the learning disabled students. Learning disabled students who get high creative stimulation, cognitive encouragement, acceptance and permissiveness at their school have been found to have better planning skills. On the other hand, learning disabled students who get low rejection and control at their school have been found to have better planning skills.

Keywords: School Environment, Planning Skills, Learning Disabled Boys and Learning Disabled Girls.

Introduction

Learning disability is defined as a permanent, objective cognitive-neurological disorder that significantly affects an individual's learning ability (Mafra, 2015). Learning disabled students are individuals who have significant difficulties in acquiring and using academic skills, despite having average or above-average intelligence. These difficulties are not due to external factors like inadequate teaching, cultural differences, or other disabilities such as visual or hearing impairments. Instead, learning disabilities stem from neurological differences that affect how the brain processes information. Students with learning disabilities often face significant challenges with planning skills. Planning, a key executive function, involves the ability to set goals, develop steps to achieve them and adjust as necessary. These skills are critical for academic success and everyday functioning. Learning disabled students may struggle to define clear and achievable objectives. They might set goals that are too broad or unrealistic, leading to frustration. They face difficulty in breaking down large tasks into smaller and manageable steps. They have problems with organizing the steps in a logical sequence. They face challenges in distinguishing between high-priority and low-priority tasks. They struggle to manage and prioritize multiple tasks simultaneously. They have limited

ability to monitor progress and stay on track. They feel difficulty in adjusting plans based on feedback or changes in circumstances.

Learning disabled students have difficulty in organizing thoughts and information coherently. A learning handicap makes it harder for a person to learn and apply specific abilities (Lerner, 2002). It has been pointed out by many scholars and researchers that students with learning disability face social, emotional and psychological problems (Lufi, Elner, & Levi, 2004). Children with learning disability face many psychosocial challenges and experience emotional and behavioural problems (Dyson, 2004). Children with learning disabilities present significant difficulties in learning as well as in social skills (Siperstein, Glick, & Parker, 2009). A child with learning disability appears to exhibit emotional problems. They have trouble expressing their feelings, calming themselves down, and reading nonverbal cues.

Students with undetected learning disabilities might demonstrate undesirable behaviour. They might feel angry, sad, lonely, frustrated, or hopeless (Neeraja, 2013). Alexi, Rappo, & Pepi (2014) showed that children with Learning disabilities have poor scholastic performance and may create feelings of anxiety, inadequacy and shame and significant stress. The associated features with learning disabled students are low self-esteem, demoralization, social skills deficits, dropping out of school, and difficulties in employment and social adjustment (Kohli, Sharma, & Padhy, 2018). Schools play a crucial and formative role in the spheres of cognitive, language, emotional, social and moral development of a child. Development of the skills also depends on the school and its environment. Especially in the case of learning disabled students, the role of school environment may be extremely crucial. Keeping it in mind the researcher tried to investigate the effect of school environment on the planning skills of learning disabled students.

Statement of the Problem

Effect of School Environment on the Planning Skills of Learning Disabled Boys and Girls.

Objectives

The objective of the present study is to examine the effect of different dimensions of school environment on the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls.

Hypotheses of the Study

Following null hypotheses have been formed in the present study:

1. There is no significant effect of creative stimulation dimension of school environment on the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls.
2. There is no significant effect of cognitive encouragement dimension of school environment on the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls.
3. There is no significant effect of acceptance dimension of school environment on the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls.
4. There is no significant effect of permissiveness dimension of school environment on the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls.
5. There is no significant effect of rejection dimension of school environment on the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls.
6. There is no significant effect of control dimension of school environment on the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls.

Methodology

1. **Method of the Study:** The researcher has used descriptive survey method in this study.
2. **Sample and Sampling Technique:** The investigator adopted random sampling technique in the present study. The researcher selected twenty five secondary schools of district Haridwar randomly. The investigator identified the learning disabled students through the administration of Learning Disabilities Battery developed by Rajshree Bhargava and R. L. Bhardwaj. Then the

investigator selected sixteen learning disabled students from the identified learning disabled students from each school. In this way, the investigator selected the required four hundred learning disabled students randomly.

3. **Variables:** Planning Skill is the dependent variable and school environment is the independent variable of the present study.
4. **Research Scale Used:** School Environment Inventory developed by K.S. Misra and Meta-Cognitive Skills Scale developed by Madhu Gupta and Suman have been used to collect the data.
5. **Statistical Techniques:** Mean, S.D. and two-way analysis of variance have been used for the statistical analysis.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Table - 1(a): Mean and S.D. of the Effect of Creative Stimulation dimension of School Environment on the Planning Skills of the Learning Disabled Boys and Girls

Variable	Gender	Creative Stimulation	Planning Skills		N
			Mean	S.D.	
Effect of Creative Stimulation on Planning Skills	Boys	High	34.53	8.85	39
		Average	29.35	7.72	48
		Low	26.34	8.28	113
		Total	28.66	8.80	200
	Girls	High	34.33	8.48	30
		Average	35.65	8.31	63
		Low	30.04	10.06	107
		Total	31.82	9.46	200
	Total	High	34.44	8.63	69
		Average	31.79	8.31	111
		Low	28.14	9.35	220
		Total	30.24	9.26	400

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis, 2024.

The table 1(a) shows the mean and S.D. of the effect of creative stimulation dimension of school environment on the planning skills of the learning disabled boys and girls. The mean values of the planning skills of learning disabled boys who get high, average and low creative stimulation at their school are 34.53, 29.35 and 26.34 respectively. These values indicate that learning disabled boys who get high, average and low creative stimulation at their school have below average, low and very low planning skills respectively.

The mean values of the planning skills of learning disabled girls who get high, average and low creative stimulation at their school are 34.33, 35.65 and 30.04 respectively. These values indicate that learning disabled girls who get high and average creative stimulation at their school have below average planning skills while learning disabled girls who get low creative stimulation at their school have low planning skills. It is also clear from the table that learning disabled students who get high creative stimulation at their school have better planning skills while learning disabled students who get low creative stimulation at their school have least planning skills.

Table - 1(b): Analysis of Variance for the Effect of Creative Stimulation dimension of School Environment on the Planning Skills of the Learning Disabled Boys and Girls

Source	SS	df	MS	F-value	Results
Gender	533.320	1	533.320	6.873**	Significant
Creative Stimulation	2284.463	2	1142.232	14.721**	Significant
Interaction	243.198	2	121.599	1.567	Insignificant
Between Group	3712.028	5	742.406		
Within Group	30571.962	394	77.594		

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis, 2024. ** = Significant at 0.01 level.

The table 1(b) shows the analysis of variance for the effect of creative stimulation dimension of school environment on the planning skills of the learning disabled boys and girls. It is clear that at df 1 and 394, the first obtained F-value for the comparison of the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls is 6.873 (Sig. = 0.01), which is significant. It shows that there is significant difference in the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls. At df 2 and 394, the second obtained F-value for the effect of creative stimulation on the planning skills of the learning disabled students is 14.721 (Sig. = 0.01), which is significant. It shows that there is a significant effect of creative stimulation on the planning skills of the learning disabled students. At df 2 and 394, the third obtained F-value for the joint effect of gender and creative stimulation on the planning skills of the learning disabled students is 1.567, which is non-significant. It shows that interaction of gender and creative stimulation has not affected the planning skills of the learning disabled students. It may be concluded that "There is no significant effect of creative stimulation dimension of school environment on the planning skills of the learning disabled boys and girls" is mostly rejected and partly accepted.

Table - 2(a): Mean and S.D. of the Effect of Cognitive Encouragement dimension of School Environment on the Planning Skills of the Learning Disabled Boys and Girls

Variable	Gender	Cognitive Encouragement	Planning Skills		N
			Mean	S.D.	
Effect of Cognitive Encouragement on Planning Skills	Boys	High	33.65	8.57	38
		Average	30.11	9.26	51
		Low	26.28	7.83	111
		Total	28.66	8.80	200
	Girls	High	30.00	8.40	13
		Average	30.08	9.01	50
		Low	30.89	9.63	137
		Total	31.82	9.46	200
	Total	High	33.49	8.45	51
		Average	32.07	9.31	101
		Low	28.83	9.14	248
		Total	30.24	9.26	400

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis, 2024.

The table 2(a) shows that the mean values of the planning skills of learning disabled boys who get high, average and low cognitive encouragement at their school are 33.65, 30.11 and 26.28 respectively. These values indicate that learning disabled boys who get high and average cognitive encouragement at their school have low planning skills while learning disabled boys who get low cognitive encouragement at their school have very low planning skills. The mean values of the planning skills of learning disabled

girls who get high, average and low cognitive encouragement at their school are 30.00, 30.08 and 30.89 respectively. These values indicate that learning disabled girls who get high, average and low cognitive encouragement at their school have low planning skills. It is also clear from the table that learning disabled students who get high cognitive encouragement at their school have better planning skills while learning disabled students who get low cognitive encouragement at their school have least planning skills.

Table - 2(b): Analysis of Variance for the Effect of Cognitive Encouragement dimension of School Environment on the Planning Skills of the Learning Disabled Boys and Girls

Source	SS	df	MS	F-value	Results
Gender	392.797	1	392.797	4.958*	Significant
Cognitive Encouragement	1362.215	2	681.108	8.598**	Significant
Interaction	231.560	2	115.780	1.462	Insignificant
Between Group	3072.331	5	614.466		
Within Group	31211.659	394	79.217		

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis, 2024.

** = Significant at 0.01 level. * = Significant at 0.05 level.

The table 2(b) shows the analysis of variance for the effect of cognitive encouragement dimension of school environment on the planning skills of the learning disabled boys and girls. It is clear that at df 1 and 394, the first obtained F-value for the comparison of the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls is 4.958 (Sig. = 0.05), which is significant. It shows that there is significant difference in the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls. At df 2 and 394, the second obtained F-value for the effect of cognitive encouragement on the planning skills of the learning disabled students is 8.598 (Sig. = 0.01), which is significant. It shows that there is a significant effect of cognitive encouragement on the planning skills of the learning disabled students. At df 2 and 394, the third obtained F-value for the joint effect of gender and cognitive encouragement on the planning skills of the learning disabled students is 1.462, which is non-significant. It shows that interaction of gender and cognitive encouragement has not affected the planning skills of the learning disabled students. It may be concluded that "There is no significant effect of cognitive encouragement dimension of school environment on the planning skills of the learning disabled boys and girls" is mostly rejected and partly accepted.

Table - 3(a): Mean and S.D. of the Effect of Acceptance dimension of School Environment on the Planning Skills of the Learning Disabled Boys and Girls

Variable	Gender	Acceptance	Planning Skills		N
			Mean	S.D.	
Effect of Acceptance on Planning Skills	Boys	High	32.24	8.89	49
		Average	28.09	9.15	61
		Low	27.10	8.03	90
		Total	28.66	8.80	200
	Girls	High	34.19	8.57	36
		Average	33.38	9.82	50
		Low	30.39	9.39	114
		Total	31.82	9.46	200
	Total	High	33.07	8.76	85
		Average	30.47	9.78	111

	Low	28.94	8.56	204
	Total	30.24	9.26	400

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis, 2024.

The table 3(a) shows the mean and S.D. of the effect of acceptance dimension of school environment on the planning skills of the learning disabled boys and girls. The mean values of the planning skills of learning disabled boys who get high, average and low accepted environment at their school are 32.24, 28.09 and 27.10 respectively. These values indicate that learning disabled boys who get high accepted environment at their school have low planning skills while learning disabled boys who get average and low accepted environment at their school have very low planning skills. The mean values of the planning skills of learning disabled girls who get high, average and low accepted environment at their school are 34.19, 33.38 and 30.39 respectively. These values indicate that learning disabled girls who get high accepted environment at their school have below average planning skills while learning disabled girls who get average and low accepted environment at their school have low planning skills. It is also clear from the table that learning disabled students who get high accepted environment at their school have better planning skills while learning disabled students who get low accepted environment at their school have least planning skills.

Table - 3(b): Analysis of Variance for the Effect of Acceptance dimension of School Environment on the Planning Skills of the Learning Disabled Boys and Girls

Source	SS	df	MS	F-value	Results
Gender	1060.621	1	1060.621	13.116**	Significant
Acceptance	1212.604	2	606.302	7.498**	Significant
Interaction	138.804	2	69.402	0.858	Insignificant
Between Group	2422.763	5	484.553		
Within Group	31861.227	394	80.866		

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis, 2024. ** = Significant at 0.01 level.

The table 3(b) shows the analysis of variance for the effect of acceptance dimension of school environment on the planning skills of the learning disabled boys and girls. It is clear that at df 1 and 394, the first obtained F-value for the comparison of the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls is 13.116 (Sig. = 0.01), which is significant. It shows that there is significant difference in the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls. At df 2 and 394, the second obtained F-value for the effect of acceptance on the planning skills of the learning disabled students is 7.498 (Sig. = 0.01), which is significant. It shows that there is a significant effect of acceptance on the planning skills of the learning disabled students. At df 2 and 394, the third obtained F-value for the joint effect of gender and acceptance on the planning skills of the learning disabled students is 0.858, which is non-significant. It shows that interaction of gender and acceptance has not affected the planning skills of the learning disabled students. It may be concluded that "There is no significant effect of acceptance dimension of school environment on the planning skills of the learning disabled boys and girls" is mostly rejected and partly accepted.

Table - 4(a): Mean and S.D. of the Effect of Permissiveness dimension of School Environment on the Planning Skills of the Learning Disabled Boys and Girls

Variable	Gender	Permissiveness	Planning Skills		N
			Mean	S.D.	
	Boys	High	32.22	9.23	71
		Average	28.52	7.98	55
		Low	25.35	7.68	74

Effect of Permissiveness on Planning Skills	Girls	Total	28.66	8.80	200
		High	34.49	8.82	83
		Average	33.13	9.40	37
		Low	28.45	9.21	80
		Total	31.82	9.46	200
	Total	High	33.44	9.05	154
		Average	30.38	8.83	92
		Low	26.96	8.62	154
		Total	30.24	9.26	400

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis, 2024.

The table 4(a) shows that the mean values of the planning skills of learning disabled boys who get high, average and low permissive environment at their school are 32.22, 28.52 and 25.35 respectively. These values indicate that learning disabled boys who get high permissive environment at their school have low planning skills while learning disabled boys who get average and low permissive environment at their school have very low planning skills.

The mean values of the planning skills of learning disabled girls who get high, average and low permissive environment at their school are 34.49, 33.13 and 28.45 respectively. These values indicate that learning disabled girls who get high, average and low permissive environment at their school have below average, low and very low planning skills respectively. It is also clear from the table that learning disabled students who get high permissive environment at their school have better planning skills while learning disabled students who get low permissive environment at their school have least planning skills.

Table - 4(b):
Analysis of Variance for the Effect of Permissiveness dimension of School Environment on the Planning Skills of the Learning Disabled Boys and Girls

Source	SS	df	MS	F-value	Results
Gender	1022.066	1	1022.066	13.421**	Significant
Permissiveness	3234.584	2	1617.292	21.236**	Significant
Interaction	76.719	2	38.359	0.504	Insignificant
Between Group	4278.150	5	855.630		
Within Group	30005.840	394	76.157		

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis, 2024. ** = Significant at 0.01 level.

The table 4(b) shows that at df 1 and 394, the first obtained F-value for the comparison of the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls is 13.421 (Sig. = 0.01), which is significant. It shows that there is significant difference in the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls. At df 2 and 394, the second obtained F-value for the effect of permissiveness on the planning skills of the learning disabled students is 21.236 (Sig. = 0.01), which is significant. It shows that there is a significant effect of permissiveness on the planning skills of the learning disabled students. At df 2 and 394, the third obtained F-value for the joint effect of gender and permissiveness on the planning skills of the learning disabled students is 0.504, which is non-significant. It shows that interaction of gender and permissiveness has not affected the planning skills of the learning disabled students. It may be concluded that "There is no significant effect of permissiveness dimension of school environment on the planning skills of the learning disabled boys and girls" is mostly rejected and partly accepted.

Table - 5(a): Mean and S.D. of the Effect of Rejection dimension of School Environment on the Planning Skills of the Learning Disabled Boys and Girls

Variable	Gender	Rejection	Planning Skills		N
			Mean	S.D.	
Effect of Rejection on Planning Skills	Boys	High	28.04	8.22	72
		Average	26.08	8.28	57
		Low	31.36	9.15	71
		Total	28.66	8.80	200
	Girls	High	27.58	10.21	53
		Average	33.64	8.90	88
		Low	32.91	8.51	59
		Total	31.82	9.46	200
	Total	High	27.84	9.08	125
		Average	30.67	9.39	145
		Low	32.06	8.86	130
		Total	30.24	9.26	400

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis, 2024.

The table 5(a) shows the mean and S.D. of the effect of rejection dimension of school environment on the planning skills of the learning disabled boys and girls. The mean values of the planning skills of learning disabled boys who get high, average and low rejected environment at their school are 28.04, 26.08 and 31.36 respectively. These values indicate that learning disabled boys who get high and average rejected environment at their school have very low planning skills while learning disabled boys who get low rejected environment at their school have low planning skills. The mean values of the planning skills of learning disabled girls who get high, average and low rejected environment at their school are 27.58, 33.64 and 32.91 respectively. These values indicate that learning disabled girls who get high rejected environment at their school have very low planning skills while learning disabled girls who get average and low rejected environment at their school have low planning skills. It is also clear from the table that learning disabled students who get high rejected environment at their school have least planning skills while learning disabled students who get low rejected environment at their school have better planning skills.

Table - 5(b): Analysis of Variance for the Effect of Rejection dimension of School Environment on the Planning Skills of the Learning Disabled Boys and Girls

Source	SS	df	MS	F-value	Results
Gender	807.594	1	807.594	10.249**	Significant
Rejection	1176.775	2	588.387	7.467**	Significant
Interaction	1151.633	2	575.817	7.308**	Significant
Between Group	3238.551	5	647.710		
Within Group	31045.439	394	78.796		

Source: Researcher's Data Analysis, 2024. ** = Significant at 0.01 level.

The table 5(b) shows the analysis of variance for the effect of rejection dimension of school environment on the planning skills of the learning disabled boys and girls. It is clear that at df 1 and 394, the first obtained F-value for the comparison of the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls is 10.249 (Sig. = 0.01), which is significant. It shows that there is significant difference in the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls. At df 2 and 394, the second obtained F-value for the effect of rejection on the planning skills of the learning disabled students is 7.467 (Sig. = 0.01), which is significant. It shows that there is a significant effect of rejection on the planning skills

of the learning disabled students. At df 2 and 394, the third obtained F-value for the joint effect of gender and rejection on the planning skills of the learning disabled students is 7.308 (Sig. = 0.01), which is significant. It shows that interaction of gender and rejection has significantly affected the planning skills of the learning disabled students. It may be concluded that “There is no significant effect of rejection dimension of school environment on the planning skills of the learning disabled boys and girls” is totally rejected.

Table - 6(a): Mean and S.D. of the Effect of Control dimension of School Environment on the Planning Skills of the Learning Disabled Boys and Girls

Variable	Gender	Control	Planning Skills		N
			Mean	S.D.	
Effect of Control on Planning Skills	Boys	High	25.54	7.74	55
		Average	30.02	8.96	44
		Low	29.77	8.94	101
		Total	28.66	8.80	200
	Girls	High	24.00	8.95	35
		Average	32.59	7.97	42
		Low	33.78	8.99	123
		Total	31.82	9.46	200
	Total	High	24.94	8.22	90
		Average	31.27	8.54	86
		Low	31.97	9.17	224
		Total	30.24	9.26	400

Source: Researcher’s Data Analysis, 2024.

The table 6(a) shows the mean and S.D. of the effect of control dimension of school environment on the planning skills of the learning disabled boys and girls. The mean values of the planning skills of learning disabled boys who get high, average and low controlled environment at their school are 25.54, 30.02 and 29.77 respectively. These values indicate that learning disabled boys who get high controlled environment at their school have very low planning skills while learning disabled boys who get average and low controlled environment at their school have low planning skills.

The mean values of the planning skills of learning disabled girls who get high, average and low controlled environment at their school are 24.00, 32.59 and 33.78 respectively. These values indicate that learning disabled girls who get high controlled environment at their school have very low planning skills while learning disabled girls who get average and low controlled environment at their school have low planning skills. It is also clear from the table that learning disabled students who get high controlled environment at their school have least planning skills while learning disabled students who get low controlled environment at their school have better planning skills.

Table - 6(b): Analysis of Variance for the Effect of Control dimension of School Environment on the Planning Skills of the Learning Disabled Boys and Girls

Source	SS	df	MS	F-value	Results
Gender	228.491	1	228.491	3.011	Insignificant
Control	3179.025	2	1589.512	20.943**	Significant
Interaction	477.668	2	238.834	3.147*	Significant
Between Group	4380.991	5	876.198		
Within Group	29902.999	394	75.896		

Source: Researcher’s Data Analysis, 2024.

** = Significant at 0.01 level.

* = Significant at 0.05 level.

The table 6(b) shows the analysis of variance for the effect of control dimension of school environment on the planning skills of the learning disabled boys and girls. It is clear that at df 1 and 394, the first obtained F-value for the comparison of the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls is 3.011, which is non-significant. It shows that there is no significant difference in the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls. At df 2 and 394, the second obtained F-value for the effect of control on the planning skills of the learning disabled students is 20.943 (Sig. = 0.01), which is significant. It shows that there is a significant effect of control on the planning skills of the learning disabled students. At df 2 and 394, the third obtained F-value for the joint effect of gender and control on the planning skills of the learning disabled students is 3.147 (Sig. = 0.05), which is significant. It shows that interaction of gender and control has significantly affected the planning skills of the learning disabled students. It may be concluded that "There is no significant effect of control dimension of school environment on the planning skills of the learning disabled boys and girls" is mostly rejected and partly accepted.

Conclusions

1. There has been found a significant difference in the planning skills of learning disabled boys and girls. Learning disabled girls have been found to have better planning skills as compared to learning disabled boys.
2. A significant effect of creative stimulation has been found on the planning skills of the learning disabled students. Learning disabled students who get high creative stimulation at their school have been found to have better planning skills.
3. Interaction of gender and creative stimulation has not been found to affect the planning skills of the learning disabled students.
4. There has been found a significant effect of cognitive encouragement on the planning skills of the learning disabled students. Learning disabled students who get high cognitive encouragement at their school have been found to have better planning skills.
5. Interaction of gender and cognitive encouragement has not been found to affect the planning skills of the learning disabled students.
6. There has been found a significant effect of acceptance on the planning skills of the learning disabled students. Learning disabled students who get high accepted environment at their school have been found to have better planning skills.
7. Interaction of gender and acceptance has not been found to affect the planning skills of the learning disabled students.
8. There has been found a significant effect of permissiveness on the planning skills of the learning disabled students. Learning disabled students who get high permissive environment at their school have been found to have better planning skills.
9. Interaction of gender and permissiveness has not been found to affect the planning skills of the learning disabled students.
10. There has been found a significant effect of rejection on the planning skills of the learning disabled students. Learning disabled students who get low rejected environment at their school have been found to have better planning skills.
11. Interaction of gender and rejection has significantly affected the planning skills of the learning disabled students. Learning disabled girls who get low rejected environment at their school have been found to have better planning skills.
12. There has been found a significant effect of control on the planning skills of the learning disabled students. Learning disabled students who get low controlled environment at their school have been found to have better planning skills.
13. Interaction of gender and control has significantly affected the planning skills of the learning disabled students. Learning disabled girls who get low controlled environment at their school have been found to have better planning skills.

Implications of the Study

Schools can implement a variety of strategies and programs to improve the planning skills of learning-disabled students. These strategies should focus on enhancing executive function skills, providing structured support and fostering independence. Schools should provide explicit instruction on planning, organization, time management, and goal-setting. Schools should integrate programs that focus on developing executive function skills into the regular curriculum. Teachers should use visual schedules to help students understand the sequence of their daily activities. They should use apps and software designed to aid in organization and planning, such as calendar apps, reminder apps and task management tools. School authorities should provide access to resource rooms where students can receive additional support and guidance on planning and organization. Learning specialists or coaches should be employed to work with students on developing their planning skills. It should be ensure that IEPs include specific goals and strategies related to improving planning skills. Teachers should model effective planning and organizational strategies, followed by guided practice with students. Students should be paired with peers who excel in planning and organization to provide mentorship and support. Collaborative projects should be encouraged where students can practice planning and organizing tasks together. School should provide positive reinforcement for successful planning and organization efforts. On-going professional development should be provided for teachers on how to support executive function skills in learning disabled students.

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